

**BRIGHT
SPACE**

Designing a Roadmap for Effective and Sustainable Strategies for Assessing and Addressing the Challenges of EU Agriculture to Navigate within a Safe and Just Operating Space

Deliverable D1.1 (D01) An operational concept for dimensions and indicators of the SJOS

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Table of Contents

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	1
1. INTRODUCTION.....	2
2. THE SAFE AND JUST OPERATING SPACE CONCEPT	5
2.1. ENVIRONMENTAL CEILINGS: THE SAFE OPERATING SPACE (SOS)	5
2.2. SOCIAL FOUNDATIONS: THE JUST OPERATING SPACE (JOS).....	9
2.3. INTERDEPENDENCIES OF ENVIRONMENTAL CEILINGS AND SOCIAL FOUNDATIONS ...	11
3. DOWNSCALING AND DISAGGREGATING THE SAFE AND JUST OPERATING SPACE	13
3.1. DOWNSCALING THE SJOS.....	13
3.2. DISAGGREGATING THE SJOS	14
4. SJOS AND EU PUBLIC POLICIES	16
4.1. SJOS FOR EU AGRICULTURE AND EUROPEAN GREEN DEAL OBJECTIVES	16
4.2. CAP OBJECTIVES AND THE SJOS	18
5. THEMATIC AREAS AND INDICATOR DOMAINS FOR EU AGRICULTURE	24
5.1. SAFE AND JUST DIMENSIONS IN THE CONTEXT OF EU POLICY OBJECTIVES.....	24
5.2. PROPOSED SJOS FOR EU AGRICULTURE.....	26
6. INVENTORY OF INDICATOR SYSTEMS	29
6.1. INDICATOR SYSTEM OF THE CAP (CMEF/PMEF)	29
6.2. INDICATOR SYSTEMS FROM PREVIOUS PROJECTS AND INITIATIVES	31
6.2.1. MIND STEP	31
6.2.2. FLINT	33
6.2.3. PROSA	34
6.2.4. INDICATORS PROPOSED BY INTEGRATED ASSESSMENT COMMUNITY	35
7. TOWARDS A BRIGHTSPACE SJOS INDICATOR FRAMEWORK	36
7.1. THEMATIC SEMINAR ON THEMATIC AREAS AND INDICATOR DOMAINS (ONLINE, 30.10.2023)	36
7.2. MODELLING WORKSHOP (HYBRID, MARCH 2024)	40
7.3. THEMATIC SEMINAR ON BIODIVERSITY INDICATORS (ONLINE, 11.04.2024)	43
7.4. NEXT STEPS.....	47
8. CONCLUSIONS AND OUTLOOK	48
9. ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS	48
10. REFERENCES.....	49
10.1. MODEL DOCUMENTATIONS.....	49
10.1. EUROPEAN COMMISSION (EC) COMMUNICATIONS.....	49
10.2. LITERATURE	50

LIST OF FIGURES

FIGURE 1 METHODOLOGY USED TO DEFINE A SJOS FOR EU AGRICULTURE	4
FIGURE 2 SIX ON THE NINE PB ARE NOW TRANSGRESSED ACCORDING TO RICHARDSON ET AL. (2023) 6	
FIGURE 3 OVERSHOOTS OF ENVIRONMENTAL CEILINGS AND SHORTFALLS OF SOCIAL FOUNDATIONS IN THE SJOS/DOUGHNUT ACCORDING TO RAWORTH (2017)	10
FIGURE 4 LINKS OF THE AGRI-FOOD OBJECTIVES OF THE EGD WITH THE DIMENSIONS OF A POSSIBLE SJOS FOR EU AGRICULTURE	17
FIGURE 5 SPECIFIC POLICY OBJECTIVES OF THE CAP 2023-27	19
FIGURE 6 CAP OBJECTIVES IN THE DOUGHNUT PERSPECTIVE.....	21
FIGURE 7 MAPPING SOS AND JOS TO CAP AND EGD OBJECTIVES.....	25
FIGURE 8 THEMATIC AREAS AND INDICATOR DOMAINS OF THE SJOS FOR EU AGRICULTURE.....	28
FIGURE 9 HIERARCHY OF THE CAP INDICATOR SYSTEM	29
FIGURE 10: SUSTAINABILITY THEMES AS INCLUDED IN THE FLINT DATA COLLECTION	33
FIGURE 11 BREAKDOWN OF PARTICIPANTS OF THE 1 ST THEMATIC WORKSHOP BY CATEGORY AND REGION.....	36
FIGURE 12 DISTRIBUTION “YES”/”NO” RESPONSES BY PARTICIPANTS TO THE QUESTION “DO YOU MISS ANY INDICATOR DOMAINS IN THE THEMATIC AREA...”	37
FIGURE 13 BRIGHTSPACE MODEL TOOLBOX	41
FIGURE 14 MURAL DASHBOARD FOR THE FARMLAND BIRD INDEX.....	45
FIGURE 15 SCORE FOR BIODIVERSITY INDICATORS BY PARTICIPANTS	46
FIGURE 16 PAIN POINTS FOR THE BIODIVERSITY INTACTNESS INDEX (BII)	47

LIST OF TABLES

TABLE 1 COVERAGE OF EARTH SYSTEM PROCESSES (SOS PROCESSES OR DOMAINS) AND INDICATORS (SOS CONTROL VARIABLES)	7
TABLE 2 COVERAGE OF JOS DOMAINS AND INDICATORS ACCORDING TO DIFFERENT AUTHORS.....	10
TABLE 3 SOS DIMENSIONS AND EGD OBJECTIVES	17
TABLE 4 JOS DIMENSIONS AND EGD OBJECTIVES.....	18
TABLE 5 CAP SPECIFIC OBJECTIVES	20
TABLE 6 SOS DIMENSIONS AND CAP OBJECTIVES	22
TABLE 7 JOS DIMENSIONS AND CAP OBJECTIVES	23
TABLE 8 SOS THEMATIC AREAS AND INDICATOR DOMAINS	26
TABLE 9 JOS THEMATIC AREAS AND INDICATOR DOMAINS.....	27
TABLE 10 SOS THEMATIC AREAS, INDICATOR DOMAINS, AND EXAMPLE CAP PMEF IMPACT INDICATORS	30
TABLE 11 JOS THEMATIC AREAS, INDICATOR DOMAINS, AND EXAMPLE CAP IMPACT INDICATORS ..	30

TABLE 12 MIND STEP INDICATOR FRAMEWORK - THEMES AND RESPECTIVE NUMBER OF INDICATORS, STRUCTURED ACROSS THE THREE DIMENSIONS OF SUSTAINABILITY	32
TABLE 13 COMMENTS BY SEMINAR PARTICIPANTS TO SOS THEMATIC AREAS AND INDICATOR DOMAINS	37
TABLE 14 COMMENTS BY SEMINAR PARTICIPANTS TO JOS THEMATIC AREAS AND INDICATOR DOMAINS	38
TABLE 15 SOS INDICATOR DOMAINS AND POTENTIAL MODEL INDICATORS.....	41
TABLE 16 JOS INDICATOR DOMAINS AND POTENTIAL MODEL INDICATORS	42

LIST OF ACRONYMS

Abbreviation/acronym	Meaning
AGMEMOD	AGricultural MEmber State MODelling
BD30	BioDiversity strategy for 2030
BII	Biodiversity Intactness Index
CAP	Common Agricultural Policy
CAPRI	Common Agricultural Policy Regionalised Impact Modelling System
CH4	Methane
CMEF	Common Monitoring and Evaluation Framework
CO2	Carbon dioxide
CO2e	Carbon dioxide equivalents in terms of Global Warming Potential
EC	European Commission
EGD	European Green Deal
EU	European Union
EuroCARE	EuroCARE GmbH Bonn
F2FS	Farm to Fork Strategy
FAO	Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations
FBI	Farmland Birds Index
FLINT	Farm Level Indicators for New Topics in Policy
GLOBIOM	Global Biosphere Management Model
GWP	Global Warming Potential
IIASA	International Institute for Applied Systems Analysis
IMAGE	Integrated Model to Assess the Global Environment
INRAE	Institut national de recherche pour l'agriculture, l'alimentation et l'environnement
JOS	Just Operating Space
LULUCF	Land Use, Land-Use Change and Forestry

Abbreviation/acronym	Meaning
MAGNET	Modular Applied GeNeral Equilibrium Tool
MIND STEP	Modelling INdividual Decisions to Support The European Policies related to agriculture
MS	Member State
MSA	Mean Species Abundance Index
N2O	Nitrous oxide
PB	Planetary Boundaries
PBL	Planbureau voor de Leefomgeving
PMEF	Performance Monitoring and Evaluation Framework
PROSA	PROgress towards Sustainable Agriculture
SDG	Sustainable Development Goals
SJOS	Safe and Just Operating Space
SOS	Safe Operating Space
Thuenen	Thünen Institute
UBO	University of Bonn
UCSC	Università Cattolica del Sacro Cuore
UN	United Nations
WR	Wageningen Research
WUR	Wageningen University and Research

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The European Green Deal (EGD) aims to enhance the role of EU agriculture in addressing climate change, managing natural resources, ensuring fair returns for farmers, and protecting biodiversity. It acknowledges the necessity for certain systemic changes throughout the EU agriculture and food system. As a key part of the EGD, the Farm to Fork Strategy outlines the Commission's commitment to leading this shift towards a sustainable food system. This involves monitoring progress towards specific targets and objectives, requiring a framework considering environmental, economic, and social aspects. Various indicator frameworks exist that encompass certain aspects of food systems and report on the advancement of relevant goals and objectives, including the UN Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) and the indicator framework of the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) .

SDG-related frameworks and the CAP's monitoring systems have intersections but differ in scope and scale. The "Doughnut" concept by Raworth (2012, 2017) combines environmental and socio-economic dimensions into a Safe and Just Operating Space (SJOS), gaining attention from academics and policymakers. The challenge lies in implementing and disaggregating the SJOS concept, particularly for specific sectors like agriculture.

This report proposes an SJOS framework tailored to EU agriculture, combining environmental, economic, and social dimensions to monitor progress towards political goals. It follows a design phase, involving a literature review, alignment with EU policy objectives, and expert consultations. The proposed SJOS consists of 12 thematic areas and 34 indicator domains, with specific indicators yet to be finalized.

The next steps involve integrating reporting for identified indicators into existing models, enabling comparisons across methodologies, and projecting indicator trajectories until 2050. Results will be discussed with stakeholders to identify Safe and Just ranges for the indicators during a dedicated retreat. This will be the starting point for the identification of Safe and Just ranges for the identified indicators.

1. INTRODUCTION

The European Green Deal (EGD, EC 2019), aims, among others, to increase the contribution of EU agriculture to climate change action, improve the management of natural resources, ensure a fair economic return for farmers, and reinforce the protection of biodiversity (EC, 2020a, 2020b).

However, current trends show that reaching EGD agricultural targets will not be an easy task. EU agricultural greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions were reducing up until the 2010s and have slightly increased since. Considerable changes in farming practices and systems are now required to achieve further substantial reductions, including a reduction in the use of nitrogen fertilization and in the number of animals farmed. Biodiversity erosion occurs due to increasingly specialised and simplified agricultural systems and rural landscapes, using larger plots of land and the widespread application of chemical inputs. Soil degradation and nutrient flows - notably nitrogen - in water and the atmosphere have reached alarming levels. With the possible exception of phosphorus and antibiotics, past trends show that it will be extremely difficult to achieve the climatic and environmental targets of the Green Deal without substantial inflexion of the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) (Guyomard, Bureau, et al., 2020). Monitoring the progress towards the general objectives and the specific targets of the EGD for the European agri-food system requires specifying and operationalizing the objectives and targets in the form of a framework that takes the relevant ecological, economic, and social aspects into account. In recent years, a variety of indicator frameworks to monitor the progress towards politically defined goals have been developed. Prominent examples are the UN Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), which notably incorporate parts of the planetary boundaries originally developed by Rockström et al. (2009) and revised in 2015 (Steffen et al., 2015) and 2023 (Richardson et al., 2023). In the general context of climate neutrality by 2050, the EGD sets several political objectives for the EU agri-food system. While some of these objectives are defined in terms of quantitative targets (for example, 50% reduction of pesticide use by 2030), other remain less precise (for example, healthy and sustainable diets). Furthermore, even when objectives are quantitative and clearly defined, they raise important questions (for example, reference period from which the pesticide reduction must be calculated, reduction percentages in each Member State (MS), etc.) and are defined as means indicators expected to decrease the environmental footprint of EU agriculture and not as indicators based on its environmental performance. For its part, the new CAP, in place since January 2023 for the five-year period 2023-2027, sets 9 specific objectives for the EU agricultural sector covering the three dimensions of sustainability (economic, environmental and social). However, CAP objectives are defined in very general terms and do not include quantitative targets. The Performance Monitoring and Evaluation Framework (PMEF 2023) of the CAP includes a large list of context-, result-, and impact-indicators to help assessing the performance of the policy measures. But precisely this sheer amount of sometimes overlapping indicators creates a challenge for the selection of indicators and the tractability of monitoring processes. In the case of the CAP, the way policy objectives are defined requires also to define specific indicators to measure the achievement of policy objectives.

SDG-related indicator frameworks have been put forward by the FAO (FAO 2020), Fanning et al. (2022) or van Vuuren et al. (2022). In a general way, the various indicator frameworks, including the PMEF (2023) for the CAP, often overlap in their contents (e.g. biodiversity) and differ in the scale and scope to which they are applied. As expected, the indicators related to the bio-physical environment are dominant with recent exceptions completing the framework by indicators related to socio-economic dimensions (Raworth 2012, O'Neill 2018, Fanning et al. 2022, van Vuuren et al. 2022, Custodio et al. (2023). The Doughnut concept developed by Raworth (2012) is an important example as it combines environmental and socio-economic dimensions and their indicators into the concept of a Safe and Just Operating Space (SJOS).

Given the large amount of established indicator frameworks, the question arises on whether, yet another one is necessary. As noted by van Vuuren et al. (2022) and Fanning et al. (2022), the number of indicators to measure, for instance, the progress towards the UN SDGs is rather large and difficult

to use in applied analyses. These authors propose to use a sub-set of these indicators selected based on their validity and availability. In addition, ongoing EU policy programs like the EGD, notably the Farm to Fork Strategy, or the CAP require more specific monitoring than in the case of the SDGs. An example is the explicitly stated 50% reduction of pesticide use in EU farming or the 20% reduction in mineral nitrogen fertilizer applications. A further consideration is that the mentioned policy strategies are aiming specifically at the agricultural sector and food systems.

The SJOS framework is a powerful concept as it provides a systematic monitoring framework that combines ecological, economic, and social aspects. This is the reason why it is increasingly studied by academics (O'Neill et al. 2018, Fanning et al. 2022, Custodio et al. 2023) and used by policymakers. A major challenge to make the concept operational for EU agriculture is its downscaling (i.e., its implementation at a scale of a region) and its disaggregating (i.e., its application for a specific sector or industry). This operationalisation raises numerous theoretical and practical questions.

In this general context, the main objective of this deliverable is to propose a SJOS for EU agriculture that takes established concepts into account but focusses on the specificities of a region (the EU), a sector (agriculture) and related policy goals (CAP and EGD objectives). The purpose is to define a framework that allows monitoring the status of EU agriculture, today and tomorrow (through different scenarios) relatively to such a SJOS that combines environmental, economic and social dimensions in a tractable and valid manner. This indicator framework is intended to be included in a standardized set of result indicators to measure potential future trajectories for EU agriculture using a set of quantitative, forward-looking tools.

This study contributes to the existing literature by proposing a set of dimensions for monitoring advancements to, or deviations from, specific policy goals for the agricultural sector in the EU. To derive such a monitoring framework from comparable examples, this paper follows the general procedure proposed by van Vuuren et al. (2022) who distinguishes the design phase, which encompasses the definition of principles and selection criteria, and the target space formulation, which starts with the selection of indicators and continues with the selection of target values (ranges of values to take into account uncertainty) (Figure 1). In this deliverable, the focus is on the design phase (dark blue boxes in Figure 1). The starting point is a review of recent literature on planetary boundaries (safe dimension of SJOS) and social foundations (just dimension of SJOS), as well as the associated indicator systems. Fanzo et al. (2023) distinguish between “thematic areas” and related “indicator domains”, which adds a very useful structural layer when comparing the SJOS dimensions across different frameworks. Following the literature review, a list of preliminary thematic areas and indicator domains was identified and compared with EU policy objectives. This framework was further discussed with internal and external experts and step-wise refined.

Figure 1 Methodology used to define a SJOS for EU agriculture

Source: Adapted from van Vuuren et al. 2022

The remainder of this report is organized according to the work steps depicted as design phases in Figure 1 Chapter 2 provides an overview of the concepts for safe and just operating spaces as defined in the literature. In chapter 3, the challenges arising from downscaling and disaggregating the concepts from global- and economy-wide contexts to the narrower space of EU agriculture are discussed. EU-specific goals and targets that can be considered to develop a SJOS for EU agriculture are reviewed in chapter 4 and used to put forward the thematic areas and indicator domains for a BrightSpace SJOS in chapter 5.

Based on the identified thematic areas and indicator domains, existing indicator systems are reviewed in chapter 6. These indicators, which were over the last year discussed with the BrightSpace partners and stakeholders are described in chapter 7, which proposes a list of indicators in each domain.

2. THE SAFE AND JUST OPERATING SPACE CONCEPT

The concept of Safe and Just Operating Space (SJOS), first introduced by Raworth (2012, 2017), adds to the physical and ecological processes of planetary boundaries (Rockström et al. 2009, Steffen et al. 2015, Richardson et al. 2023) the additional dimension corresponding to social well-being at global scale. The initial ambition of the just dimension is to change the “compass” that has been set by economic approach of monitoring wealth and its distribution. The criticism of the Gross Domestic Product (GDP) approach is very much in line with the report on “Limits to Growth” (Meadows et al. 1972) and the work of the Stiglitz-Sen-Fitoussi Commission (Stiglitz et al. 2009). In addition, Raworth’s criticism of the concept of economic growth has to be contrasted with the fact that without technical change and growth, transitions to a more sustainable world are likely to be more difficult to implement. However, the fact that markets do not value damages such as pollution or depletion of non-renewable resources in a price that reflects their social values is undisputable. Moreover, Raworth also signals the importance of a trend in the current society that fosters waste and overconsumption, leading to additional negative spillovers on both the environment and social dimensions.

Achieving sustainable development means ensuring that all people have the resources needed – such as food, water, health care or energy – to fulfil their human rights. And it means ensuring that humanity’s use of natural resources does not stress critical Earth system processes – by causing climate change or biodiversity loss, for example – to the point that Earth is pushed out of the stable state, known as the Holocene, which has been so beneficial to humankind over the past 10,000 years.

2.1. Environmental ceilings: the Safe Operating Space (SOS)

Environmental ceilings correspond to the safe dimension. They rely on the Safe Operating Space (SOS) concept first proposed by Rockström et al. (2009) who argued that nine Planetary Boundaries (PB) must not be transgressed to maintain the Earth system in a desired state (Holocene-like state). These PB are ceiling values (thresholds) that the control variables of nine key processes of the Earth system (one or more control variables for each process) must not be transgressed. Because processes are very sensitive around threshold levels, crossing these thresholds are likely to generate severe and possibly irreversible changes (Green et al. 2017). Defining the PB and the corresponding thresholds that must be not transgressed poses conceptual and empirical problems.

Rockström et al. (2009) considered nine Earth System processes: 1) Climate change, 2) Ocean acidification, 3) Stratospheric ozone depletion, 4) Atmospheric aerosol loading, 5) Biogeochemical flows: interference with P and N cycles, 6) Global freshwater use, 7) Land-system change, 8) Rate of biodiversity loss, and 9) Chemical pollution. They were not able to determine thresholds for two processes (chemical pollution and atmospheric aerosol loading). For the seven other processes for which they were able to determine PB, they found that three were already transgressed (climate change, rate of biodiversity loss, and changes to the global nitrogen cycle). Rockström et al. (2009) underlined that “their planetary boundaries [were] rough, first estimates only, surrounded by large uncertainties and knowledge gaps”.

Six years later, Steffen et al. (2015) provided a revised and extended analysis of their initial SOS framework in which they changed the names of several processes, updated control variables and the previous quantification of several PB, were able to quantify the PB for one of the two PB that were quantified earlier, and introduced a two-tier approach for several PB, “reflecting the importance of cross-scale interactions and the regional-level heterogeneity of the processes that underpin the boundaries. According to their updated results, four processes exceeded the proposed PB, that is: climate change, biosphere integrity, biogeochemical flows, and land-system change. On these four transgressed PB, two (climate change and biosphere integrity) are considered by Steffen et al. (2015) as the two “core planetary boundaries through which the other boundaries operate” (proposition of

“a two-level hierarchy of boundaries”). Each of these core PB has the potential on its own to drive the Earth system into a new state should they be substantially and persistently transgressed.

Very recently, Richardson et al. (2023) proposed a second revision of the PB framework in which they concluded that six of the nine PB are now transgressed, that is: climate change, biosphere integrity, land system change, freshwater change, biogeochemical flows, and novel entities. Furthermore, the “transgression level has increased for all boundaries earlier identified as overstepped.” This is illustrated by Figure 2.

Figure 2 Six on the nine PB are now transgressed according to Richardson et al. (2023)

Source: <https://www.science.org/cms/10.1126/sciadv.adh2458/asset/64f1671e-2c90-4811-bf74-7997cd547d1f/assets/images/large/sciadv.adh2458-f1.jpg>

Table 1 presents the nine processes of the Earth System considered in the works of the Stockholm Resilience Centre (SRC) with their respective names according to the publication (Rockström et al., 2009, Steffen et al., 2015, Richardson et al., 2023). It also provides the control variables used characterizing each process. While the nine processes remained unchanged, their control variables have changed.

Table 1 Coverage of Earth System processes (SOS processes or domains) and indicators (SOS control variables)

Rockström et al. 2009a/b		Steffen et al. 2015		Richardson et al. 2023		Fanzo et al. 2023	
Earth System Process	Control variable	Earth System Process	Control variable	Earth System Process	Control Variable	Process	Control Variable
Climate change	Atmospheric CO2 concentration, ppm Energy imbalance at top-of atmosphere, W m ⁻²	Climate Change	Atmospheric CO2 concentration, Energy imbalance at top-of atmosphere	Climate Change	Atmospheric CO2 concentration, Energy imbalance at top-of atmosphere	Greenhouse gas emissions	
Ocean acidification	Carbonate ion concentration, average global surface ocean saturation state with respect to aragonite	Ocean acidification	Carbonate ion concentration, average global surface ocean saturation state with respect to aragonite (Warag)	Ocean Acidification	Carbonate ion concentration, average global surface ocean saturation state with respect to aragonite (Qarag)		
Stratospheric ozone depletion	Stratospheric O3 concentration, Dobson Unit (DU)	Stratospheric ozone depletion	Stratospheric O3 concentration, DU	Stratospheric ozone depletion	Stratospheric O3 concentration, (global average) (DU)		
Biogeochemical flows: Interference with the Global Phosphorus and Nitrogen Cycles	P: inflow of phosphorus to ocean, increase compared with natural background weathering N: amount of N2 removed from atmosphere for human use, Mt N yr ⁻¹	Biogeochemical flows: Nitrogen and phosphorous cycles	P Global: P flow from freshwater systems into the ocean P Regional: P flow from fertilizers to erodible soils N Global: Industrial and intentional biological fixation of N	Biogeochemical flows: P and N cycles	Phosphate global: P flow from freshwater systems into the ocean; regional: P flow from fertilizers to erodible soils (Tg of P year ⁻¹) Nitrogen global: Industrial and intentional fixation of N (Tg of N year ⁻¹) y		
Global freshwater use	Consumption of freshwater by humans (km ³ per year)	Freshwater use	Global: Maximum amount of consumptive bluewater use (km ³ yr ⁻¹) Basin: Blue water withdrawal as % of mean monthly riverflow	Freshwater change	Blue water: human induced disturbance of blue water flow Green water: human induced disturbance of water available to plants (% land area with deviations from preindustrial variability)	Water use	
Change in land use	Percentage of global land cover converted to cropland	Land-system change	Global: Area of forested land as % of original forest cover Biome: Area of forested land as % of potential forest	Land-Use Change	Global: area of forested land as the percentage of original forest cover; biome: area of forested land as the percentage of potential forest (% area remaining)	Land use	

Rockström et al. 2009a/b		Steffen et al. 2015		Richardson et al. 2023		Fanzo et al. 2023	
Rate of biodiversity loss	Extinction rate, extinctions per million species per year (E/MSY)	Change of biosphere integrity: Genetic diversity, functional diversity	Genetic diversity: Extinction rate Functional diversity: Biodiversity Intactness Index (BII)	Change in biospheric integrity	Functional integrity: measured as energy available to ecosystems (NPP) (% HANPP) Genetic diversity: E/MSY	Biosphere integrity Agro-biodiversity	
Atmospheric aerosol loading	Overall particulate concentration in the atmosphere, on a regional basis	Atmospheric aerosol loading	Global: Aerosol Optical Depth (AOD), but much regional variation Regional: AOD as a seasonal average over a region. South Asian Monsoon used as a case study	Atmospheric aerosol loading	Inter hemispheric difference in AOD	Pollution	
Chemical pollution		Introduction of novel entities		Percentage of synthetic chemicals released to the environment without adequate safety testing			

While noting that “the PB framework is not designed to be ‘down-scaled’ or ‘disaggregated’ to smaller levels, such as nations or local communities”, Steffen et al. (2015) underline that “the PB framework recognizes the importance of changes at the level of subsystems in the Earth system (e.g., biomes or large river basins) on the functioning of the Earth system as a whole. Also, there are strong arguments for an integrated approach coupling boundary definitions at regional and global levels with development goals to enable the application of ‘PB thinking’ at levels (nations, basins, and regions) where policy action most commonly occurs.”

On a different point, they underline that “the PB framework does not dictate how societies should develop. These are political decisions that must include consideration of the human dimensions, including equity, not incorporated in the PB framework.” The concept of a SJOS extends that of a SOS by including justice and equity foundations (hereafter called social foundations), more generally by bringing the human dimension in.

2.2. Social foundations: the Just Operating Space (JOS)

Raworth (2012, 2017) completed the SOS concept by adding the social foundations of human well-being in that framework with the objective of defining “*a radically new compass for guiding humanity this century*” (Raworth, 2017, p.44). Starting from a criticism of the way economists monitor economic health using GDP growth, she argues that politics and economics lose sight of their goals that are to “*ensure prosperity for all within the means of our planet*” (Raworth, 2017, p.32). Then, she proposes a social foundation based on the basics of life, which no one should be left falling short.

The first version of the social foundation proposed by Raworth (2012) included 11 dimensions of well-being, the boundary of each being zero deprivation. The choice of these dimensions was based on the analysis of the states’ contributions to the United Nations Conference on Sustainable Development Rio+20 in 2012. She collected these priorities from more than half of the states (Raworth, 2017). These social priorities were grouped into 3 clusters depending on their objectives: (i) enabling people to be well (priorities of food security, decent revenue, clean water, and health); (ii) enabling people to be productive (priority of education, decent job, access to energy, and resilience to shocks); (iii) enabling people to be empowered (priorities of gender equality, social equity, and having a political voice). An alternative way of classifying these priorities can be based on their nature: (i) access to goods (such as sufficient food, clean water, and energy), (ii) access to public services (such as health, and education), and (iii) social and political contexts and governance (such as gender equality, social equity, political voice, access to decent job and income, and resilience to shocks in particular through social protection schemes).

Social boundaries were slightly re-defined in Raworth (2017): decent housing, peace and justice, access to networks of information and social support were introduced while resilience to shocks was removed. Indeed, resilience to shocks can be viewed as the result of other social and environmental dimensions (Cole et al. 2014). These social boundaries are consistent with elements contained in the Universal Declaration of Human Rights (UN, 1948) and are included in the United Nations SDGs. As for PB, global indicators at the humanity level are suggested, based on international statistics, some priorities being more difficult than others to monitor (for instance freedom of expression).

The joint consideration of the safe and just spaces leads to the definition of a SJOS commonly depicted in the form of a doughnut (Figure 2). This figure encompasses both the environmental ceilings of the Earth System, which must not be transgressed, and the social foundations of the Humanity, which must be satisfied. It shows the environmental ceilings that are overshoot and the social foundations that are in shortfall according to Raworth (2017).

Figure 3 Overshoots of environmental ceilings and shortfalls of social foundations in the SJOS/Doughnut according to Raworth (2017)

Table 2 presents the various domains (processes) with their corresponding indicators (control variables) proposed by different authors (Raworth 2012, 2017, 2022, O'Neill 2018, Fanning et al. 2022, Fanzo et al. 2023) to define and characterize the social foundations of the Doughnut. This table shows that both domains and indicators are less homogenized for the just space than for the safe space. On that perspective, Custodio et al. (2023) listed 1389 socioeconomic indicators from a systematic review approach. They showed that these indicators are mostly used in high-income level countries, notably in the EU MS. They also argue that “developing indicators is not an end in itself. It is a mean of influencing decision-making, and it is therefore important to understand the intended use of indicators” (Custodio et al., p8.).

Table 2 Coverage of JOS domains and indicators according to different authors

Raworth 2012/2017 /2022		Fanning et al. 2022, O'Neill et al. 2018		Fanzo et al. 2023	
Process	Control variable	Process	Control variable	Process	Control variable
Food security	Population undernourished	Nutrition	Food supply [kcal per capita and day]	Diets, nutrition, and health: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Diet quality • Food security • Food environments Policies affecting food environments	Global Diet Quality Score
Health care	Population estimated to be without regular access to essential medicines	(Healthy) Life Expectancy	Life expectancy at birth [Years]		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Prevalence of undernourishment • Food availability Access To Nutrition Index (ATNI)
Gender equality	Employment gap between women and men in waged work (excluding agriculture)				

Raworth 2012/2017 /2022		Fanning et al. 2022, O'Neill et al. 2018		Fanzo et al. 2023	
Income and work	Population living below USD 1.25 (PPP) per day	Income	Population earning above USD 5.50 per day (2011 PPP) [%]	Livelihoods, poverty, and equity: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Poverty and income Employment Social protection Rights 	Livelihoods key indicators International Labour Organization employment statistics World Bank Social Safety Nets Reporting The Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (FAO) Gender and Land Database
		Employment	Labour force employed [%]		
Social equity	Population living on less than the median income in countries with a Gini coefficient exceeding 0.35	Equality	Gini coefficient (equivalent to Gini index of 0.3) [0–100]		
Networks	Population stating that they are without someone to count on for help in times of trouble	Social Support	Population with friends or family they can depend on [%]		
Water and sanitation	Population without access to an improved drinking water source	Sanitation	Population with access to improved sanitation [%]		
Energy	Population lacking access to electricity	Access to Energy	Population with access to electricity [%]		
Education	Children not enrolled in primary school	Education	Gross enrolment in secondary school [%]		
Housing	Proportion of global urban population living in slum housing in developing countries				
Peace and justice	Population living in countries scoring 50 or less out of 100 in the Corruption Perceptions Index				
Political voice	Population living in countries scoring 0.5 or less out of 1.0 in the Voice and Accountability Index	Democratic Quality	Transformed Worldwide Governance Indicators [0-10]		
		Life Satisfaction	Cantril ladder scale [0–10]		

2.3. Interdependencies of environmental ceilings and social foundations

The SJOS is to provide a visual framework for sustainable development, combining planet et social boundaries. It makes it possible to discuss the interdependence of both spaces , one major challenge for the Humanity. Raworth (2017, 2022) proposes nothing less than seven ways of thinking “like a twenty-first-century economist”: (i) change the goal, meaning forgetting GDP growth objective and adopt the Doughnut framework; (ii) see the big picture based on new narratives about “the power of the market, the partnership of the state, the core role of the household and the creativity of the commons”; (iii) nurture human nature, based on the transformation of the portrait of the rationale economic man; (iv) get savvy with systems, moving from the supply and demand curves and mechanical equilibrium to take into consideration the dynamic complexity of the relation between

economic inequality and climate change; (v) design to distribute wealth beyond income, meaning controlling land, technology, research, knowledge; (vi) create to regenerate, meaning design to create circular economy and “to restore human as full participants in Earth’s cyclical processes of life”; and (vii) be agnostic about growth. However, Raworth admits that this framework does not provide answers neither specific policy prescriptions.

For example, poverty and environment stress can be positively or negatively linked, depending on policy decisions. Planet boundaries and social foundation are essentially normative. The objective of the policymakers should not be the GDP growth, but the impacts of economic and social activities on the position relatively to both on planet and social boundaries. The implementation of the Doughnut framework to imagine policies at national/regional and/or sector/industry/enterprise level needs to be imaginative and requires adapting the original SJOS framework. We discuss these points below.

3. DOWNSCALING AND DISAGGREGATING THE SAFE AND JUST OPERATING SPACE

Two challenges to make the SJOS framework operational for EU agriculture are how to shift from processes, indicators and thresholds defined for the planet to processes, indicators and thresholds defined for a particular region (the EU) and a particular sector (agriculture) These are the challenges of downscaling and disaggregating, respectively. Downscaling the SJOS means hereafter applying it to a region/country/sub-region scale while disaggregating means applying it to a specific sector/industry. An additional challenge is to link this process of downscaling and disaggregating to actual policy objectives and instruments that affect, directly or indirectly, EU agriculture. Finally, although attention is focused on agriculture, the analysis cannot ignore other actors of the food chain as well as impacts of agricultural policies on these other actors, for example on consumers through food security variables, indicators, and thresholds. In this Chapter 3, the literature addressing the two issues of downscaling and disaggregating in a general way is addressed. Subsequently, in Chapter 4 the way operationalize the SJOS framework for EU agriculture is explained.

3.1. Downscaling the SJOS

The interdependent nature of the Earth System processes leads to the development of the SJOS at the planet level. Nevertheless, many authors acknowledged the need to downscale the analysis to better align the framework with decision-making scales (for example, Biermann and Kim 2020).

Downscaling the SJOS can lead to adapting some control variables and adding new ones. It also requires defining regional boundaries.. There is no unique way to define such regional boundaries even for the environmental processes. A per capita allocation key is indeed a straightforward approach used, for example, by Nykvist et al. (2013) for Sweden or by Hoff et al. (2014) for Europe. Alternative allocation keys such as economic weight or “historical responsibility” were suggested by Fang et al. (2015). Choosing a specific sharing rule for defining safe regional boundaries for control variables of a given process results thus from a choice made by the authors of any regional SOS. In that sense, it is a “political” choice that cannot ignore policy objectives relevant for the territory under consideration. However, policy objectives set by policymakers cannot simply and immediately be supposed to be equal to the safe and just regional boundaries (and there is no policy target for each safe and just dimension). In other words, policy objectives provide useful information that must be analyzed in detail and used with care to define regional boundaries. More generally, it is crucial to specify the assumptions adopted to define each regional boundary and to analyze the position of the territory, today and tomorrow in the context of different scenarios of evolution, considering these assumptions. Indeed, this political choice is closely linked with the just foundations of the SJOS. Indeed, it must consider a large set of dimensions such as fairness, equity, capacity to act or country’s economic development (Häyhä et al. 2018). Furthermore, for most of the boundaries, thresholds should have different values depending on the regions of the territory considered, which can differ in local environmental pressures, the vulnerability of ecosystems, agro-ecological conditions, etc. Häyhä et al. (2018) argued that biophysical, socio-economic and ethical dimensions can be considered as nested dimensions: the biophysical dimensions dominate and determine the pertinent geographic scale to analyze socio-economic dynamics, which itself conditions the ethical choices.

In that perspective, a distinction can be made between two categories of biophysical processes (Häyhä et al. 2016). The first category includes the processes that generate truly global public goods. Typically, climate change, ocean acidification, ozone depletion are part of this category. “For these processes, the absolute magnitude of anthropogenic emissions is what determines the overall impact, and it does not substantially matter where on Earth the emissions are generated” (Häyhä et al. 2016). Therefore, the boundaries can be universal. But, how to achieve a fair distribution of the reduction efforts to not

exceed the PB? For global public goods, the principle of common but differentiated responsibility” attempts to consider means and capacities of nations and of their populations, industries and public services in handling environmental problems.

The second category includes the processes for which local human activity impacts the Earth System essentially on a local scale. Such processes correspond to local public goods (i.e. aerosol loading, loss of biodiversity, biogeochemical flows of nutrients, land use changes and freshwater). For these processes, national allocation of the global SOS cannot simply consist in sharing a global budget because local conditions, including temporal variability, play a crucial role in determining the level of sustainable use or tolerable emissions, and in opening opportunities for socioeconomic and equity co-benefits. For instance, Fang et al. (2015) proposed downscaled boundaries for water and land based on regional resource availabilities. For water, they proposed to set the country boundary at a percentage as a percentage of total renewable water resources, that is the sum of internal and external water resources of that country. At this stage, it is important to emphasize that pure local public goods are uncommon (this is the case, for example, of biodiversity conservation). Very often, they share characteristics of local and global public goods, which clearly increases the difficulty in defining corresponding regional boundaries.

An additional difficulty is linked to the “perspective” adopted for the downscaling and is directly related to the consideration of exports and imports. A production-based approach (also called territorial approach) traces emissions or resource use linked to the production that is consumed locally or exported. Imports are thus excluded. By contrast, a consumption-based approach traces emissions or resource use linked to the consumption of products that are produced locally or imported. Exports are thus excluded. The value of using both approaches simultaneously can be illustrated by considering the case of a country that imports a large part of its consumption with very few exports or, on the contrary, exports a large part of its production with very few imports. In the first case, consumption-based indicators of the safe regional space will be much higher than production-based indicators. It is the opposite in the second case.

As already mentioned, Custodio et al. (2023) provided an overview of wellbeing indicators that can be used for EU MS, the main lesson of this work being that the choice of adequate indicators depends on the investigated question. Considering the “broad definition” of the JOS leads to include the fact that remaining in a SOS requires allocation of efforts that should be governed by equity and justice considerations (O’Neill et al. 2018). Nevertheless, some of wellbeing indicators refer to moral values that differ between regions and populations. Different countries have different degrees of aversion to inequality. Religions interfere with these values in different ways (e.g. gender equality is not perceived the same way throughout the EU MS, more generally the world countries). Different moral values make it particularly difficult to come up with well-accepted criteria for defining an ideal benchmark. Although these social norms and moral values differ from one country to another, including from a European MS to another, we propose to make the undoubtedly simplifying assumption that European MS are socially and culturally homogeneous.

3.2. Disaggregating the SJOS

The focus on EU agriculture implies not only a geographical downscaling of the SJOS but also a disaggregation of the EU SJOS between sectors. The disaggregating issue raises similar difficulties as those quoted above for downscaling, notably the choice of the sharing key and of several sharing keys for defining thresholds that must be not transgressed or must be respected in the sector considered. There is no unique way to define sharing rules and the choice can have a considerable impact on results. For example, an allocation rule based on economic criteria will favor sectors that generate high value added or financial outputs. An allocation rule based on a grandfathering or “status quo” approach relying on past benchmarks will favor established economic sectors, while new activities will

have eventually more effort for regional limits to be met. It is therefore necessary to be transparent on sharing rules and to consider the sensitivity of results to the choice of a given sharing rule. One option is to use several sharing rules and to assess the sensitivity of the downscaled and disaggregated SJOS to these choices. A second difficulty, perhaps even more important, is the choice of processes and control variables that define the social foundations of a SJOS for the sector considered.

Focusing on climate change, Krabbe et al. (2015) proposed to differentiate the shares allocated to an activity sector depending on its technological potential for reducing GHG emissions, with a smaller share when the potential is low and a higher share when the potential is significant. They concluded that results are particularly sensitive to the choice of sharing principles for defining a national and product SOS, but also to the life cycle analysis of the sector production. Ryberg et al. (2018) both downscaled and disaggregated the SOS in a study focused on a specific sector, specifically a virtual laundry washing industry in the EU. They compared the boundaries obtained from three allocation rules corresponding to (i) a per-capita allocation, (ii) an allocation based on value added, and (iii) an allocation based on final consumption expenditure. For their part, Buckwell and Nadeu (2018) defined a simplified SOS for the EU livestock sector. They considered two “bad” environmental outputs (GHG and ammonia emissions) with two upper boundaries and two “good” environmental outputs (nutrition and pasture) with two lower boundaries. Respective boundaries were as follows: for climate change, the upper boundary was based on the definition of reduction targets following the Paris Climate Agreement assuming that “livestock are to contribute the same as other [economic activity] sectors; for nitrogen, the upper boundary was based on the level of protein necessary to provide adequate nutrition for the EU population; for nutrition, the lower boundary was based on national nutritional recommendations differentiated by MS and animal product that should not be exceeded; finally, for pasture, the lower boundary was based on the number of ruminants by hectare of permanent grassland that are required to maintain permanent grasslands. They concluded that EU livestock is not in a SOS since the four boundaries are transgressed.

Two points must be discussed to progress in defining the inner circle of a SJOS for EU agriculture: Which dimensions of the social foundations of the Doughnut are relevant for this sector? Which benchmarks can be used, relative or absolute targets? In other words, is it necessary to choose the social foundations to be retained, their control variables and their boundaries. Roy and Paramanick (2019) analysed various socioeconomic agricultural indicators that are linked to social foundations. Specifically, they considered agricultural value added, income and employment, as well as the share of agriculture in male and female employment; these indicators are in turn connected to UN SDGs 1, 5 and 8. They also considered two additional socioeconomic variables (job and gender equality) also retained by Raworth (2017) as two social foundations. Nevertheless, these authors did not propose thresholds for these different indicators. They “only” provided an illustration of regional heterogeneities among the various MS regarding these different indicators.

4. SJOS AND EU PUBLIC POLICIES

Defining both the planetary environmental ceilings (PB/SOS) and humanity's social foundations (JOS) presents a challenge due to the absence of a single method for downscaling (to country/region level) and disaggregating (by product/industry/sector) the SJOS. In essence, this is because of the normative nature of determining safe and just thresholds and, more importantly, allocating them to specific countries/regions and/or sectors/industries/products. Public policies and their targets can help to address this challenge.

This can be accomplished at the global/humanity level in relation to the UN SDGs and for EU agriculture in connection with EGD and CAP objectives. As the focus of the BrightSpace project is on developing a SJOS for EU agriculture, the next chapters will explore the linkages to EU policy objectives.

4.1. SJOS for EU agriculture and European Green Deal objectives

The EGD (EC 2019) encompasses a set of policy initiatives and strategies that aim to set EU on the path to a green transition, with the overarching goal to achieve climate neutrality by 2050 and support the transformation of the EU into a fair and prosperous society with a modern and competitive economy. While it addresses the whole economy across all sectors, it is very relevant for the agricultural and food sector. This relevance was highlighted by Guyomard, Bureau et al. (2020), who identified the main initiatives of the EGD that affect agriculture. Among those are the Farm to Fork Strategy, the Biodiversity Strategy, and the Climate Law. The EU Soil Strategy adds focus on soil health in the Biodiversity Strategy.

The objectives displayed in these strategies are of immediate relevance for the definition of a SJOS for EU agriculture as they reflect important, identified environmental and societal challenges, and shape political debates and policy design. Figure 4 provides an overview on the Safe and Just dimensions of the original Doughnut (Raworth 2012) that are reflected in the EGD. Notably, there is an overlap with several dimensions of the safe space like biodiversity, land use, climate change, nitrogen and phosphorus cycles, and chemical pollution. The dimensions of the just space are less explicitly covered even if the general ambition of the EGD is “to support the transformation of the EU into a fair and prosperous society with a modern and competitive economy” (EC 2019), hence including for farmers, their salaries and their family.’ Guyomard et al. (2023) provide an overview of the quantifiable farm-gate targets of the EGD that are directly linked to some dimensions of the SOS:

- Reducing the use and risk of chemical pesticides by 50% and the use of more hazardous pesticides by 50%
- Reducing nutrient losses by at least 50% (“while ensuring no deterioration in soil fertility”) and fertilizer use by at least 20%
- Reducing the sales of antimicrobials for farm animals and aquaculture by 50%
- Achieving 25% of total farmland under organic farming
- Dedicating 10% of farmland to high-diversity landscape features

In addition to these quantitative targets, the EGD includes a number of statements and objectives that can be connected to the just dimensions.

Figure 4 Links of the agri-food objectives of the EGD with the dimensions of a possible SJOS for EU agriculture

Note: Green arrows correspond to quantitative agricultural targets of the EGD; four dimensions of the social foundations are also included (income, food, health and, to a lesser extent because only through the development of fast broadband in rural areas, social equity; furthermore, the EGD also includes an objective of lower food waste and losses that should contribute to several dimensions of the safe space

More generally, with regard to the SOS, Table 3 gives an overview on the SOS dimensions and their links to the EGD objectives, namely those stated in the Farm to Fork Strategy (F2FS, EC2020b), the Biodiversity Strategy (BD2030, EC2020a) and the Climate Ambition (CA2030, EC2020c). It appears that almost all SOS dimensions are covered by the EGD, with the exception of ocean acidification and ozone depletion.

Table 3 SOS dimensions and EGD objectives

SOS Process	Related EGD Objectives
Rate of biodiversity loss	Protecting and restoring biodiversity and well-functioning ecosystems (BD2030)
	Step up the protection and restoration of nature (BD2030)
	Protect soil fertility, reduce soil erosion and increase soil organic matter (BD2030)
Change in land use	Reversing and halting the downward trend of the LULUCF carbon sink. (CA2030)
	At least 25% of the EU’s agricultural land under organic farming (F2FS)
	At least 10% of agricultural area under high-diversity landscape features (BD2030)
Climate change	Economy wide 2030 greenhouse gas emissions reduction target of 55% (CA2030) GHG emission reduction target towards 50 or 55% compared with 1990 levels (F2FS)
Global freshwater use	Preserving and restoring [...] freshwater [...] resources (F2FS)
Biogeochemical flows: Interference with the Global Phosphorus and Nitrogen Cycles	Reduce nutrient losses by at least 50%, while ensuring that there is no deterioration in soil fertility (F2FS)
	Reduce the use of fertilisers by at least 20% by 2030 (F2FS)
Atmospheric aerosol loading	Nutrients used in agriculture [but not] effectively absorbed by plants, is another major source of air , soil and water pollution (F2FS)
Chemical pollution	Reduce the overall use and risk of chemical pesticides by 50% and the use of more hazardous pesticides by 50% by 2030 (F2FS)

SOS Process	Related EGD Objectives
	Reduce overall EU sales of antimicrobials for farmed animals and in aquaculture by 50% by 2030 (F2FS)
Ocean acidification	Not directly addressed by the EGD
Stratospheric ozone depletion	

Sources: BD2030: Biodiversity Strategy for 2030 (EC2020a), CA2030: Stepping up Europe’s 2030 climate ambition (EC2020c), F2FS: Farm to Fork strategy (EC2020b)

As indicated in Figure 4, the JOS dimensions are not covered to the same extent as the SOS dimensions. Table 4 provides the links between the EGD objectives, notably solely from the F2FS, and the JOS dimensions in Table 2.

Table 4 JOS Dimensions and EGD Objectives

JOS Process	Related EGD Objectives
Food security	Ensuring food security, nutrition (F2FS) Preserving the affordability of food (F2FS) Reducing food loss and waste (F2FS)
Health care	Facilitating the shift to healthy, sustainable diets (F2FS) Reversing the rise in overweight and obesity rates (F2FS) Protecting [...] animal health and welfare (F2FS)
Water and sanitation	Closely related to health
Energy	Closely related to climate change and income
Income and work	Strengthen the position of farmers [...], their cooperatives and producer organisations in the food supply chain (F2FS) Generating fairer economic returns in the supply chain (F2FS)
Social equity	Closely related to income
Gender equality	Closely related to income and social equity
Education	Closely related to income and social equity
Networks	Not directly addressed by EGD
Housing	
Peace and justice	
Political voice	

Sources: F2FS: Farm to Fork strategy (EC2020b)

4.2. CAP Objectives and the SJOS

The EU’s common agricultural policy (CAP) was introduced in 1962 and originally aimed mainly to:

- support farmers and improve agricultural productivity, ensuring a stable supply of affordable food;
- safeguard European Union farmers to make a reasonable living;
- help tackle climate change and the sustainable management of natural resources;
- maintain rural areas and landscapes across the EU;
- keep the rural economy alive by promoting jobs in farming, agri-food industries and associated sectors.

The CAP applies for all EU MS and is managed and funded at EU level from the resources of the EU’s budget. Responding to new situations and emerging challenges, the CAP has evolved over the years

to meet changing economic circumstances and citizens' requirements and needs. Recently, the CAP 2023-27 entered into force on 1 January 2023. The support for farmers and rural stakeholders across the EU MS is based on this legal framework and the National Strategic Plans proposed by the MS and approved by the Commission. The approved Plans are designed to make a significant contribution to the ambitions of the European Green Deal, namely the Farm to Fork Strategy and Biodiversity Strategy.

The CAP 2023-27 aims to further improve the sustainable development of farming, food and rural areas and contributes to achieving the following general objectives in the economic, environmental and social spheres, which will contribute to the implementation of the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development (EU 2021):

- to foster a smart, competitive, resilient and diversified agricultural sector ensuring long-term food security;
- to support and strengthen environmental protection, including biodiversity, and climate action and to contribute to achieving the environmental and climate-related objectives of the Union, including its commitments under the Paris Agreement;
- to strengthen the socio-economic fabric of rural areas.

These three general objectives are further split into 9 specific objectives (Figure 5, Table 5) and a 10th cross-cutting objective addressing the fostering of knowledge and innovation.

Figure 5 Specific policy objectives of the CAP 2023-27

Source: https://agriculture.ec.europa.eu/common-agricultural-policy/cap-overview/cap-2023-27/key-policy-objectives-cap-2023-27_en

Table 5 CAP Specific Objectives

Key objective	Description	Acronym
1. Supporting viable farm income	support viable farm income and the resilience of the agricultural sector across the EU, in order to enhance long-term food security and agricultural diversity, as well as to ensure the economic sustainability of agricultural production	ECO1
2. Increasing competitiveness	enhance market orientation and increase farm competitiveness both in the short and long term, including greater focus on research, technology and digitalisation	ECO2
3. Improve farmers' position in the value chain	improve farmers' position in the value chain	ECO3
4. Contributing to climate change mitigation	contribute to climate change mitigation and adaptation, including by reducing greenhouse gas emissions and enhancing carbon sequestration, as well as promoting sustainable energy	ENV1
5. Efficient natural resource management	foster sustainable development and efficient management of natural resources such as water, soil and air, including by reducing chemical dependency	ENV2
6. Halting and reversing biodiversity loss	contribute to halting and reversing biodiversity loss, enhance ecosystem services and preserve habitats and landscapes	ENV3
7. Support generational renewal	attract and sustain young farmers and new farmers and facilitate sustainable business development in rural areas	SOC1
8. Jobs, growth and equality in rural areas	promote employment, growth, gender equality, including the participation of women in farming, social inclusion and local development in rural areas, as well as the circular bio-economy and sustainable forestry	SOC2
9. Responding to societal demands on food and health	improve the response of EU agriculture to societal demands on food and health, including high-quality, safe and nutritious food produced in a sustainable way, to reduce food waste, as well as to improve animal welfare and combat antimicrobial resistance	SOC3
10. Fostering knowledge and innovation	modernise agriculture and rural areas through fostering and sharing knowledge, innovation and digitalisation, and by encouraging their uptake by farmers through improved access to research, innovation, knowledge exchange and training	CC

Sources: https://agriculture.ec.europa.eu/common-agricultural-policy/cap-overview/cap-2023-27/key-policy-objectives-cap-2023-27_en, EU 2021

As in the case of the EGD in the previous chapter, the CAP objectives are highly relevant for and closely connect to the SJOS (Figure 6). In contrast to the EGD, the CAP covers a wider range of JOS dimensions like gender equality or social inclusion.

Figure 6 CAP objectives in the Doughnut perspective

The links between SOS dimensions and CAP objectives are shown in more detail in Table 6. One important observation is that the CAP objectives cut across several SOS dimensions. For instance, objective ENV3 makes reference to the reversion of biodiversity losses and also to the preservation of landscapes and habitats. Among the impact indicators used to measure the achievement of the objective is “Increasing agro-biodiversity in farming system: Crop diversity” (Policy Monitoring and Evaluation Framework, PMEF 2023). This links to the biodiversity and land use dimension of the SOS. At the same time, ENV2 mentions efficient management of natural resources like soil, for instance measured by “Reducing soil erosion: Percentage of agricultural land in moderate and severe soil erosion” (PMEF 2023), which also relates to aspects of the land use dimension.

In addition to soil, objective ENV2 covers also water and air and refers to the reduction of chemical dependency. The related impact indicators in the PMEF are:

- I.14 Improving air quality: Ammonia emissions from agriculture
- I.15 Improving water quality: Gross nutrient balance on agricultural land
- I.16 Reducing nutrient leakage: Nitrates in ground water – percentage of ground water stations with nitrates concentration over 50 mg/l under Directive 91/676/EEC
- I.17 Reducing pressure on water resource: Water Exploitation Index Plus (WEI+)
- I.18 Sustainable and reduced use of pesticides: Risks, use and impacts of pesticides

Based on these impact indicators, the SOS dimensions related to freshwater use, phosphorus and nitrogen cycles, atmospheric aerosol loading, and chemical pollution are jointly addressed in this specific CAP objective.

Objective ENV1 covers climate change mitigation and adaptation, including the reduction of GHG emissions and carbon sequestration. While these objectives are closely linked, the indicator “Enhancing carbon sequestration: Soil organic carbon in agricultural land” is also connected to land use practices.

Ocean acidification and stratospheric ozone depletion are not directly addressed in the CAP objectives.

A general observation is therefore that the CAP objectives ENV1 to ENV3 include many aspects of the SOS in a cross-cutting way. The linkage between SOS and CAP are more evident at the level of detailed impact and context indicators (PMEF 2023).

Table 6 SOS Dimensions and CAP Objectives

SOS Process	Related CAP Objectives
Rate of biodiversity loss	ENV3: Contribute to halting and reversing biodiversity loss, enhance ecosystem services and preserve habitats and landscapes
Change in land use	
Global freshwater use	
Biogeochemical flows: Interference with the Global Phosphorus and Nitrogen Cycles	ENV2: Foster sustainable development and efficient management of natural resources such as water, soil and air, including by reducing chemical dependency
Atmospheric aerosol loading	
Chemical pollution	
Climate change	ENV1: Contribute to climate change mitigation and adaptation, including by reducing greenhouse gas emissions and enhancing carbon sequestration, as well as promoting sustainable energy
Ocean acidification	<i>Not directly addressed by the CAP</i>
Stratospheric ozone depletion	

As in the case of the SOS, the CAP objectives cover a wide range of JOS dimensions, but certain aspects of the CAP objectives correspond with several JOS dimensions. In the case of food security, ECO1 makes a clear reference to food security (although this is not addressed in the PMEF impact indicators) and SOC3 mentions safe and nutritious food, which is also part of food and nutrition security.

In contrast, the JOS dimension income and work includes a rather large number of CAP objectives, at least in parts. For instance, the impact indicators for ECO1 in the PMEF are:

- I.2 Reducing income disparities: Evolution of agricultural income compared to the general economy
- I.3 Reducing farm income variability: Evolution of agricultural income
- I.4 Supporting viable farm income: Evolution of agricultural income level by type of farming (compared to the average in agriculture)
- I.5 Contributing to territorial balance: Evolution of agricultural income in areas with natural constraints (compared to the average)

These indicators point to two aspects of the objective to support viable farm incomes as they refer not only to the level and change of income (I.3) but also to agricultural incomes compared to the rest of the economy (I.2).

Aspect of work and employment are addressed in SOC2, which also relates to social equity and gender equality (e.g. I.24 Contributing to jobs in rural areas: Evolution of the employment rate in rural areas, including a gender breakdown).

JOS dimensions like networks, housing, peace and justice, or political voice are not directly addressed in the CAP objectives and the indicators in the PMEF.

Table 7 JOS Dimensions and CAP Objectives

JOS Process	CAP Objectives
Food security	ECO1: Support viable farm income and the resilience of the agricultural sector across the EU, in order to enhance long-term food security and agricultural diversity, as well as to ensure the economic sustainability of agricultural production
Health care	SOC3: Improve the response of EU agriculture to societal demands on food and health , including high-quality, safe and nutritious food produced in a sustainable way, to reduce food waste , as well as to improve animal welfare and combat antimicrobial resistance
Water and sanitation	<i>Closely related to health</i>
Energy	<i>Closely related to climate change and income</i>
Income and work	ECO1: Support viable farm income and the resilience of the agricultural sector across the EU, in order to enhance long-term food security and agricultural diversity, as well as to ensure the economic sustainability of agricultural production ECO2: Enhance market orientation and increase farm competitiveness both in the short and long term, including greater focus on research, technology and digitalization ; ECO3: Improve farmers' position in the value chain SOC1: Attract and sustain young farmers and new farmers and facilitate sustainable business development in rural areas
Social equity	SOC2: Promote employment, growth, gender equality , including the participation of women in farming, social inclusion and local development in rural areas , as well as the circular bio-economy and sustainable forestry
Gender equality	CC: modernise agriculture and rural areas through fostering and sharing knowledge, innovation and digitalisation, and by encouraging their uptake by farmers through improved access to research, innovation, knowledge exchange and training
Education	
Networks	
Housing	<i>Not directly addressed by the CAP</i>
Peace and justice	
Political voice	

5. THEMATIC AREAS AND INDICATOR DOMAINS FOR EU AGRICULTURE

The comparison of SOS and JOS dimensions with the EGD and CAP objectives showed that a further refinement and adjustment is needed to create a set of SJOS dimensions that connect the components found in the literature with the EU policy objectives. For this task, the distinction between “thematic areas” and “indicator domains” as used by Fanzo et al.(2023) proved to be useful because it facilitates grouping a re-arranging of items while maintaining their connection to larger thematic areas. The next chapters give an overview on the considerations related to the alignment of the SJOS dimensions identified in literature review in chapter 2 and the policy review in chapter 4.

5.1. Safe and just dimensions in the context of EU policy objectives

To arrive at a system of indicators that reflects the aspects of SOS and JOS and the EU policy objectives, the different thematic areas and indicator domains were compared item by item. Figure 7 visualizes the general concept: Items from the SOS and JOS are depicted on the left side, while CAP (colourful) and EGD (grey) objectives are on the right. The blue-shaded table in the centre is the resulting set of thematic areas and indicator domains that capture the contents from both sides.

In case of the SOS, the comparison shows a rather clear alignment between the concepts from literature reviews and policy targets, largely due to the fact that the planetary boundaries concept is already well established and reflected in policy debates. In case of the JOS, the contents are not as well aligned, although there is already overlap in certain domains, like regarding food and nutrition security.

The following paragraphs provide further details on the comparison between the dimension from literature and policy objectives.

In the SOS literature, **biodiversity** is understood as functional and genetic diversity of the biosphere, while the CAP and EGD objectives also include land management options that are supposed to be drivers for biodiversity. The EU Biodiversity Strategy, the Farm to Fork Strategy, and the CAP mention preservation of habitats and landscapes (CAP), the dedication of 10% of farmland to high-diversity landscape features (Biodiversity Strategy), or achieving 25% of total farmland under organic farming (Farm to Fork Strategy). These aspects of **land management** are closely connected to land-system change or land conversion, measured by the change of forestry area. The Climate Target Plan (EC 2020c) for instance indicates reversing and halting the downward trend of the carbon sink potential from **Land Use, Land-Use Change and Forestry (LULUCF)**. The carbon sink potential is part of the Soil Strategy, which emphasizes the importance of **soil health** to ensure that a range of ecosystem services can be provided, e.g. food and biomass production, including in agriculture and forestry (EC 2021). The efficient management of natural resources like soil, **water**, and **air**, including the prevention of **nutrient losses** is also a declared objective of the CAP and reflected in EGD strategies.

With regard to **climate change** and greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions, the planetary boundaries literature focusses on carbon dioxide (CO₂), while the agriculture-related policy targets mention methane (CH₄) and nitrous oxide (N₂O) as main GHG emitted from agriculture. Ocean acidification is a result from increased CO₂ concentration in the atmosphere and as such not a direct objective of agricultural policies. The same holds for ozone layer depletion, to which agriculture is not a major contributor.

The comparison of the SOS dimensions with the EU policy targets shows a consistent overlap, in particular with the three environmental objectives of the CAP (Figure 7, green-shaded areas) and it appears therefore as appropriate to include them in the concept of a SJOS for EU agriculture.

Literature	SJOS	CAP	EGD Strategies		
			Farm to Fork	Biodiversity	Soil
	Thematic area Indicator domains				
SOS	Biodiversity loss	Biodiversity Genetic/Functional diversity (outcomes) Land management (drivers)	Env. 3: Contribute to the protection of biodiversity, enhance ecosystem services and preserve habitats and landscapes		
	Land conversion	Land use Land cover Soil health			
	Freshwater use	Water use Water use	Env. 2: Foster sustainable development and efficient management of natural resources such as water, soil and air		
	Nitrogen and phosphorus cycles	Nutrient flows Nitrogen cycle Phosphorus cycle			
	Chemical pollution	Chemical pollution (novel entities) Pesticide use Antimicrobials			
	Atmospheric aerosol loading Climate change	Aerosol loading Air pollution (Particulates) Climate GHG emissions	Env. 1: Contribute to climate change mitigation and adaptation, as well as sustainable energy		
Ocean acidification Ozone depletion					
JOS	Food security	Nutrition security Food availability Food affordability	Eco. 1: Support viable farm income and resilience across the Union to enhance food security		
	Health	Health Diet quality/food utilization Food waste Life expectancy Obesity	Social 3: Improve the response of EU agriculture to societal demands on food and health, including safe, nutritious and sustainable food, reducing food waste, as well as animal welfare		
	Water	Water Access to clean water Animal welfare			
	Income and work	Economy Sectoral Employment Sectoral VAD Sectoral wages	Eco. 2: Increase competitiveness and agricultural productivity in a sustainable way to meet the challenges of higher demand in a resource-constrained and climate uncertain world		
	Energy	Market organisation Trade Energy access	Eco. 3: Improve farmers' position in the value chain		
		Farm resilience Farm income Farm viability Farm structure	Env. 1 Eco. 1		
	Social equity	Social equity Income distribution (sectoral, spatial)	Social 1: Modernise the agricultural sector by attracting young people and improving their business development		
	Education	Education	Social 2: Promote employment, growth, social inclusion and local development in rural areas, including bio economy and sustainable forestry		
	Gender equality	Gender equality			
		Recreational landscapes			
Housing					
Peace and justice					
Networks					
Political voice					

Figure 7 Mapping SOS and JOS to CAP and EGD objectives

Concerning the economic and social aspects in the JOS literature, it appears that food and **nutrition security, health**, including access to clean water are directly addressed by CAP end EGD strategies (namely the Farm to Fork strategy, EC 2020a), but with a different focus than at global scale. The EU policy targets emphasize more the affordability of food and healthy diets rather than food availability, which is generally not considered as insecure in EU Member States. However, recent events have shown that also food storage and self-sufficiency have to be safeguarded against at least temporary

supply shocks. Decreased life expectancy as result of unhealthy diets and obesity is more of a concern. Reduction of food waste and animal welfare are also among the objectives of the CAP.

Income and work aspects are covered by CAP and EGD objectives by targeting employment conditions in the agricultural sector, the competitiveness of EU farms, the position of farmers in the value-chain, and increased productivity of the agricultural sector. Conceptually, two aspects can be distinguished: the position of the farming sector within the national economies, expressed e.g. by wage differences between economic sectors, and the viability of farms within the agricultural sector. The CAP as well as the EGD include several aspects of farm resilience, mainly to increase the attractiveness of the farming sector for younger people. For this reason, the larger JOS dimension “income and work” is split into general **economy** and **farm resilience**, the former addressing agriculture in comparison with the rest of the economies, including energy access and prices, and the latter the economic situation and prospects within the agricultural sector.

Social equity, education, and gender equality are addressed in the CAP objective to promote vibrant and socially inclusive, prospering rural areas. The JOS dimensions housing, peace and justice, networks, and political voice (Table 7) are not directly mentioned in the CAP and EGD objectives with relation to agriculture as they refer to the larger societal and political environment and are therefore beyond the scope of agricultural policies.

5.2. Proposed SJOS for EU Agriculture

Based on literature review of the SOS and JOS concepts, the comparison and alignment with EU policy targets, and the consultation of experts, a set of 12 thematic areas and 34 indicator domains were derived. The SOS components are directly aligned with the concepts found in the literature about planetary boundaries, with the exceptions of ocean acidification and ozone layer depletion. In the case of JOS, a large overlap between literature and EU policies was found in the case of food and nutrition security as well as in the case of health. Economy-related topics were split into two thematic areas: General economy, covering the relative situation of agriculture with the rest of the economy in terms of employment, value-added, and wages, as well as input prices. Dimensions specific to the farming sector, like agricultural incomes, economic viability, prospects, and farm structure are covered by the larger thematic area “farm resilience”. The identified thematic areas and indicator domains are depicted in Figure 8.

Table 8 SOS Thematic Areas and Indicator Domains

Thematic area	Indicator Domain
Biodiversity	Genetic/Functional diversity (outcomes)
	Land management (drivers)
Land use	Land cover
	Soil health
Water use	Water use
Nutrient flows	Nitrogen cycle
	Phosphorus cycle
Chemical pollution (novel entities)	Pesticide use
	Antimicrobials
Aerosol loading	Air pollution (Particulates)
Climate	GHG emissions

Table 9 JOS Thematic Areas and Indicator Domains

Thematic area	Indicator Domain
Nutrition security	Food availability
	... affordability
	... stability
	Food waste
	Diet quality/food utilization
Health	Life expectancy
	Obesity
	Animal welfare
	Access to clean water
Economy	Sectoral employment
	Sectoral productivity
	Sectoral wages
	Market organisation
	Trade
	Energy access
Farm resilience	Farm income
	Farm viability
	Farm structure
Social equity	Income distribution (sectoral, spatial)
	Education
	Gender equality

Figure 8 Thematic areas and indicator domains of the SJOS for EU agriculture

6. INVENTORY OF INDICATOR SYSTEMS

6.1. Indicator system of the CAP (CMEF/PMEF)

As part of the CAP, a monitoring and evaluation framework has been set up. It provides key information on the CAP implementation, on its results and on its impacts. It quantifies the actions in the different Member States, describes their achievements, highlights which instruments are most efficient and verify how well objectives have been reached. Basically, the monitoring system measures the fulfilment of the CAP goals, through the use of various indicators (Figure 9). Indicators are therefore tools for measuring the achievement of goals. Therefore, different sets of indicators are associated with different goals, which work differently from each other, just as the goals formulated at different levels are also different.

Accordingly, indicators exist at three different levels: output indicators give the direct 'product' of the measure (e.g. 50 energy-saving investments funded through a measure); result indicators give the direct, immediate effect of the measure/programme (e.g. 500 jobs created as a result of the investment measure). Impact indicators go beyond the direct, immediate effect but look at the longer term (e.g. rural unemployment rate). Overall, impact indicators are linked to the general objectives of the CAP, result indicators to the specific objectives and output indicators to individual policy interventions. Finally, there is a set of context indicators, which provide information on general trends of economy, state of the environment, general climate indicators, agricultural and rural statistics, etc. The context indicators are closely related to the impact indicators, since the latter measure exactly what changes have occurred as a result of the subsidies in terms of the environmental, economic and social characteristics, described by the context indicators, relating to the state before the subsidies. For this reason, the context and impact indicators are included in a common table.

Figure 9 Hierarchy of the CAP indicator system

Source: European Union, 2015 (doi:10.2762/5243)

In summary, the types of indicators are as follows:

- Output indicators: activities directly realised by interventions,
- Result indicators: direct and immediate effect of interventions,
- Impact indicators: outcome of intervention beyond immediate effects,
- Context indicators: general contextual trends.

The indicator system of the CAP has changed a lot over the years, but since the formulation of the CMEF (which happened before the 2014-2020 period), apart from minor changes, it shows roughly the same structure.

Table 10 and Table 11 present examples of CAP PME F impact indicators (PME F 2023) by SOS and JOS thematic areas and indicator domains of the proposed SJOS for EU agriculture.

Table 10 SOS Thematic Areas, Indicator Domains, and Example CAP PME F impact indicators

Thematic area	Indicator Domain	Example PME F Impact Indicator
Biodiversity	Genetic/Functional diversity (outcomes)	I.19 Increasing farmland bird populations: Farmland Bird Index
	Land management (drivers)	I.22 Increasing agro-biodiversity in farming system: Crop diversity
Land use	Land cover	I.21 Enhancing provision of ecosystem services: Share of agricultural land covered with landscape features
	Soil health	I.13 Reducing soil erosion: Percentage of agricultural land in moderate and severe soil erosion
Water use	Water use	I.17 Reducing pressure on water resource: Water Exploitation Index Plus (WEI+)
Nutrient flows	Nitrogen cycle	I.16 Reducing nutrient leakage: Nitrates in ground water – percentage of ground water stations with nitrates concentration over 50 mg/l under Directive 91/676/EEC
	Phosphorus cycle	
Chemical pollution (novel entities)	Pesticide use	I.18 Sustainable and reduced use of pesticides: Risks, use and impacts of pesticides
	Antimicrobials	I.28 Limiting antimicrobial use in farmed animals: Sales/use of antimicrobials for food-producing animals
Aerosol loading	Air pollution (Particulates)	I.14 Improving air quality: Ammonia emissions from agriculture
Climate	GHG emissions	I.10 Contributing to climate change mitigation: Greenhouse gas emissions from agriculture

Source: Own elaboration and PME F 2023

Table 11 JOS Thematic Areas, Indicator Domains, and Example CAP impact indicators

Thematic area	Indicator Domain	Example PME F Impact Indicator
Nutrition security	Food availability	
	Food affordability	
	Food access	
	Diet quality/food utilization	I.29 Responding to consumer demand for quality food: Value of production under Union quality schemes and of organic production
Health	Food waste	
	Life expectancy	
	Obesity	
	Access to clean water	
	Animal welfare	

Thematic area	Indicator Domain	Example PMEF Impact Indicator
Economy	Sectoral Employment	I.24 Contributing to jobs in rural areas: Evolution of the employment rate in rural areas, including a gender breakdown
	Sectoral VAD	I.8 Improving farmers' position in the food chain: Value added for primary producers in the food chain
	Sectoral wages	I.2 Reducing income disparities: Evolution of agricultural income compared to the general economy
	Market organisation	
	Trade	I.7 Harnessing agri-food trade: Agri-food imports and exports
	Energy access	
Farm resilience	Farm income	I.3 Reducing farm income variability: Evolution of agricultural income
	Farm viability	I.23 Attracting young farmers: Evolution of the number of new farm managers and the number of new young farm managers, including a gender breakdown
	Farm structure	
Social equity	Income distribution (sectoral, spatial)	I.27 Promoting rural inclusion: Evolution of poverty index in rural areas
	Education	
	Gender equality	I.23 Attracting young farmers: Evolution of the number of new farm managers and the number of new young farm managers, including a gender breakdown, I.24 Contributing to jobs in rural areas: Evolution of the employment rate in rural areas, including a gender breakdown

Source: Own elaboration and PMEF 2023

6.2. Indicator Systems from Previous Projects and Initiatives

6.2.1. MIND STEP

The MIND STEP (Modelling INdividual Decisions to Support The European Policies related to agriculture, H2020) project indicator framework covers the three dimensions of sustainability. Kelly et al.(2018) stressed that the contribution of a farm to sustainable agriculture involves the production of goods and services (economic dimension), the management of natural resources (environmental/ecological dimension) and the contribution to rural communities (social dimension). Consequently, assessment of policy impacts on farm's sustainability will inevitably involve these three interconnected dimensions.

Indicator are considered as a variable which supplies information on other variables which are difficult to access and which can be used as a benchmark to take a decision (Gras et al., 1989). These indicators need to be clearly connected to the nine objectives of the new CAP, particularly those linked to environment, climate, landscape and biodiversity, as proposed by the Core stakeholder Group in the first MIND STEP workshop (MIND STEP Deliverable 1.1).

In addition, the indicators need to provide information at farm level, which is central to MIND STEP. The ecological and economic interactions are most pronounced at farm level (van Wenum et al., 1999).

The big challenge is that harmonised, good quality environmental datasets to produce environmental indicators are often lacking. For example, the agri-environmental indicators (Eurostat) database contains information from which some of the CMEF indicators are derived to track the integration of environmental concerns into the CAP. However, Eurostat data are not available at farm level. There are only three datasets that are collected consistently at farm level throughout the EU on a yearly basis. They include the Farm Accountancy Data Network (FADN); the IACS (Integrated Administration and Control System) database, which manages CAP payments to farmers; and the Land Parcel Identification System (LPIS) spatial database, which is part of IACS and monitors land parcels and land use at farm level.

Table 12 MIND STEP Indicator framework - themes and respective number of indicators, structured across the three dimensions of sustainability

Dimension	Theme	Number of indicators
Economic		
	Agricultural productivity	9
	Farm income/GDP	4
	Other gainful activities	1
	Structural change	3
	Land prices	1
	Agricultural trade	2
Environmental		
	Land cover/Land use	10
	Agri-environmental commitments	1
	Feed use	1
	Energy	2
	GHG emissions	7
	Air quality	1
	Nutrient (N,P) balance	6
	Water quality	4
	Water quantity and availability	3
	Soil quality and fertility	4
	Soil erosion	1
	Biodiversity and landscapes	9
	Pesticide use	3
	Animal welfare	1
Social		
	Employment	2
	Training and education	8

Source: MIND STEP Deliverable 1.2

6.2.2. FLINT

The FLINT project (Poppe et al., 2016) addressed the growing need for data on the sustainability performance of agriculture, not only within the industry but especially among researchers and policy makers to monitor and evaluate the Common Agricultural Policy. The CAP shows a higher level of ambition to mitigate environmental and climate impacts. The shift to more environmental policies, the interplay between environmental and agricultural policies and the shift to results and performances will bring forward new data needs for monitoring and policy evaluation.

To address these needs the FLINT project (Farm Level Indicators for New Topics in policy evaluation) was created to test the feasibility of collecting sustainability data at farm level and to illustrate the value of this type of data to improve policy making. The project defined a list of relevant sustainability themes based on emerging policy needs, a literature review and a review of national initiatives to measure sustainability. The themes have been evaluated with different stakeholder. Finally, 31 themes were selected (see Figure 10 below). Each of these themes were translated in a specific list of data items to be collected at farm level.

Figure 10: Sustainability themes as included in the FLINT data collection

An important distinction with other projects focussing on developing indicator frameworks is that FLINT tested the feasibility of collecting these data and illustrating the added value of having these data.

The feasibility of collecting these data was tested by collecting the defined data items in 9 member states (Ireland, Netherlands, Germany, Poland, Finland, Hungary, Greece, Spain and France) on 1,100 farms of different farm types (Vrolijk et al., 2016). The results show that data collection is possible in the different administrative environments that member states face or have chosen to organize the national FADN. In general, the FLINT project showed positive experiences of collecting sustainability data, furthermore the project showed that farmers are willing to make the data available.

Based on the collected data, the project has shown how policy analysis benefit from additional data with indicators on the sustainability performance of farms (profit, planet and people aspects). A number of cases was selected to illustrate different aspects of these new opportunities (for example comparison of sustainability performance between countries, trade-off between different sustainability indicators and the link between specific policy measures and the broader sustainability performance of farms).

6.2.3. PROSA

The PROSA (Measuring Progress towards Sustainable Agriculture, FAO) initiative is a framework that seeks to complement ongoing efforts on the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), and particularly indicator 2.4.1, to support country-level assessments using data already available at the national level. Making agriculture more sustainable – productive, environmentally friendly, resilient and profitable is fundamental, as agriculture remains the main source of livelihood for the majority of the world’s poor and hungry. The pathway towards sustainable agriculture must ensure increasing output, but also make more efficient use of increasingly scarce global resources, be resilient to and help mitigate climate change, and improve human well-being.

Sixteen indicators were chosen for the PROSA framework for tracking sustainability in agriculture at national level, across thirteen themes. We next provide a detailed discussion of each indicator, including their FAOSTAT source and underlying data processes, with a mapping against the original SDG 2.4.1 framework and themes.

The economic dimensions were captured within the themes of land productivity, farm profitability and resilience. Trends in productivity and profitability were monitored using the following indicators:

1. Land Productivity: Gross value of production per agricultural land (constant 2004–2006 I\$/ha);
2. Farm Profitability: Gross value of production per worker (constant 2004–2006 I\$/cap);
3. Resilience 1: Credit per rural population (USD/cap); and
4. Resilience 2: Value of production diversification index (%).

Land productivity was captured by the gross total value of crop and livestock production per unit land, representing in essence a yield expressed in monetary terms. At national level it was computed as the ratio of “gross index value for agriculture” from the FAOSTAT Production Indexes (<http://www.fao.org/faostat/en/#data/QI>, 1961–2018) to “agricultural land” area from the FAOSTAT Land Use domain (<http://www.fao.org/faostat/en/#data/RL>, 1961–2018). As discussed below with respect to the dashboard, PROSA interprets negative changes as an indication of poor sustainability.

Farm profitability was monitored via the gross total value of crop and livestock production per worker. At national level it was computed as the ratio of “gross index value for agriculture” defined above to “Employment in agriculture” numbers from the FAOSTAT Employment Indicators domain (<http://www.fao.org/faostat/en/#data/OE>, 1961–2018). Similarly to the above indicator, PROSA interprets negative changes as an indication of poor sustainability.

Limitations in both indicators above is the use of gross versus net production values, i.e. costs are not included. While this is not an issue for the productivity indicators, where monetary value is used merely as a straightforward way to aggregate physical yields of widely different commodities, it is a significant limitation in terms of profitability indicators, since the latter is clearly dependent on a balance between gross income and costs, which must be assumed to remain fairly proportional to income in order for the trends assessed to be meaningful.

Economic Resilience was monitored in terms of credit to agriculture per rural population and as an index of diversification of agricultural production.

Credit to agriculture per rural population was measured through the flow of financial capital in support of production. At national level it was computed as the ratio of “credit to agriculture” from the FAOSTAT Credit to Agriculture domain (<http://www.fao.org/faostat/en/#data/IC>, 1991–2018) to “Rural population” numbers from the FAOSTAT “Population” domain (<http://www.fao.org/faostat/en/#data/OA>, 1991–2018). PROSA interprets negative changes over time as an indication of poor sustainability.

The Diversification Index captures the risk of agricultural production arising from the basket of commodities produced. At national level it was computed as the Gini coefficient relative to the gross

production value of all crop and livestock commodities in a country, taken from the FAOSTAT Production Indexes (<http://www.fao.org/faostat/en/#data/QI>; 1961–2018). PROSA interprets negative changes over time as an indication of poor sustainability.

6.2.4. Indicators proposed by integrated assessment community

Van Vuuren et al. (2022) propose a framework with indicators and a ‘target space’ based on the SDGs. They argue that the existing list of 232 indicators and 232 targets as defined by the SDG framework are too broad, unstructured and complex to support quantitative and model-based analysis of transformation pathways, and a simpler approach is needed based on a limited set of indicators that are quantifiable, actionable and can be used for long-term scenario analysis. The formulation of the target space was informed by discussion with around 60 experts that were part of the World in 2050 initiative. The process consisted of: (1) formulation of key principles for the target space and selection criteria; (2) the review of existing sets of indicators and targets in the literature, international agreements, and associated with the SDGs; and (3) the final selection of a set of indicators and targets.

The selected indicators and target space are grouped in five clusters that are based on the key elements of sustainable development introduced in the preamble of the 2030 Agenda (UN, 2015): People (SDGs 1, 3, 4 and 5); Prosperity (SDGs 8, 9, 10 and 11); Planet integrity (SDGs 13, 14 and 15); Sustainable Resource Management (SDGs 2, 6, 7, 12); Peace, institutions and implementation (SDGs 16 and 17). Table 2 in the paper present a detailed overview of the selected indicators and target space for each SDG.

7. TOWARDS A BRIGHTSPACE SJOS INDICATOR FRAMEWORK

7.1. Thematic Seminar on Thematic Areas and Indicator Domains (Online, 30.10.2023)

To ensure the validity of the SJOS concept derived from literature review and comparison with EU policy objectives, the proposed list of indicator domains (Table 8 and

Table 9, with variants of Table 10 and Table 11) was exposed to the scientists involved in the BrightSpace project during the annual meeting in Prague (October 2023) and at a later stage to the BrightSpace stakeholder community in the framework of the 1st Thematic Seminar (“Shaping the Safe and Just Operating Space: Thematic Areas, Domains and Indicators”, 30. October 2023, online). This seminar was attended by 36 persons, of which 12 were scientists directly involved in BrightSpace and 24 external participants with various backgrounds (Figure 11).

Figure 11 Breakdown of participants of the 1st Thematic Workshop by category and region

After an introduction into the BrightSpace framework, the thematic areas and the indicator domains, online polls were used to receive feedback from the stakeholder community. The first question was whether they miss any indicator domains in the respective thematic areas (Q: “Are you missing any indicator domain in the Thematic Area ‘...’?”). The responses are shown in Figure 12. Missing indicator domains were identified in most cases, with nutrient flows, climate, biodiversity, chemical pollution, and nutrition security the most prominent ones.

Figure 12 Distribution “Yes”/”No” responses by participants to the question “Do you miss any indicator domains in the thematic area...”

In a next step, participants were invited to list indicator domains or specific indicators they consider as relevant (Q: “Which indicator domain do you miss in the thematic area...”). The comments are shown in Table 13 for SOS and Table 14 for JOS Thematic Areas. For nutrient flows, it appeared that in particular gross nutrient balances of N and P should be included. For climate change, it was recommended to indicate not only total GHG emissions in CO2 equivalents but provide a breakdown into emission specific for the agricultural sector, namely CH4 and N2O. A wide range for biodiversity indicators was proposed. For land use, the inclusion of landscape features was also recommended.

Based on these recommendations, the BrightSpace SJOS concept was further refined and discussed with the modelling teams involved in BrightSpace. Because of the suggestions with regard to the biodiversity indicators, a further workshop was organized.

Table 13 Comments by Seminar Participants to SOS Thematic Areas and Indicator Domains

Thematic area	Indicator Domain	Responses to “Which indicator domain do you miss in the thematic area ...”
Biodiversity	Genetic/ Functional diversity (outcomes)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Pollinator indicator - Botanical / insect diversity - Biodiversity loss - Pressure by invasive alien species on ecosystems - Grassland butterfly index - Butterfly index
	Land management (drivers)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Share of Landscape features - Indicators linked to actual agricultural practices (e.g. shallow/no tillage areas, no pesticide use areas, for example from FADN?); indicator about landscape features e.g. from LUCAS, as a proxy for biodiversity; - Ecosystem functions - Land configuration (continuity and diversity of landscape features) - Woody landscape features
Land use	Land cover	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Under land cover: sealed areas (land covered by buildings, roads, etc); to clarify how various land cover categories will be rated, especially ANCs. - Agricultural land covered with landscape features

Thematic area	Indicator Domain	Responses to “Which indicator domain do you miss in the thematic area ...”
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Crop diversity - Land use for food, feed and biofuels - Area in Agri-Environmental Measures - Landscape elements
	Soil health	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - EUSO soil health dashboard by the JRC - Soil erosion by wind - Quality of organic matter - Amount of nutrients in arable land - Soil biodiversity - Water absorption - Soil compaction
Water use	Water use	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - irrigation - irrigated area, number of irrigated basins - Agricultural area under irrigation - Irrigable area - Reclaimed water for irrigation
Nutrient flows	Nitrogen cycle	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Gross nutrient balance nitrogen - The JRC has data on N excess in agriculture (see data in e.g. EUSO soil health dashboard) as well as P - Gross nutrient balance N P - occurrences of green tides - Chemical nitrogen use - Total nitrogen use
	Phosphorus cycle	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Gross nutrient balance phosphorus
	Other	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Other nutrients are also important - calcium based pH - Potassium cycle
Chemical pollution (novel entities)	Pesticide use	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Use of the most risky PPPs - Soil pollution by heavy metals (see again EUSO dashboard) - Contaminated sites in the EU - risk is also problematic some pesticides used in eco agriculture are considered more risky - soil contamination with toxic elements - not sales but use of pesticides, sales might be in different country - pesticides residues analyses in drinking water
	Antimicrobials	
Aerosol loading	Air pollution (Particulates)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - indicators of asthmatic or pneumopathic events in the rural population health
Climate	GHG emissions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Separate Indication of Methane, because of different interpretation of GHG effect from methane - Breakdown of CO₂, NO₂ and CH₄ emissions, to be able to see what ag sector are exceeding their limits - GHG emissions from food system - Irrigable area

Table 14 Comments by Seminar Participants to JOS Thematic Areas and Indicator Domains

Thematic area	Indicator Domain	Responses to “Which indicator domain do you miss in the thematic area ...”
Nutrition security	Food availability	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Self-sufficiency ratios of key agricultural commodities
	... affordability	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - prices - Crop commodity prices - food access

Thematic area	Indicator Domain	Responses to "Which indicator domain do you miss in the thematic area ..."
		- Consumer food inflation
	... stability	
	Diet quality/food utilization	
	Other	- Protein production efficiency index
Health	Life expectancy	- Life expectation is too broad to relate to agriculture and food - DALY - Child mortality
	Obesity	
	Animal welfare	- Livestock density is an inappropriate indicator for 'animal welfare'
	Access to clean water	- access to clean water needs to be included. Since there can be a tension between (1) fresh water usage for water-intensive crops in an area and/or irrigation and drinking water needs and (2) agriculture emissions may negatively affect the availability of clean water in an area. So it is an important indicator to monitor. - closing of drinking water catchments
	Other	- A link with mental health - Mental health related - other chronic diseases in addition to obesity (diabetes, cardiovascular diseases) - Population access to green spaces
Economy	Sectoral Employment	
	Sectoral productivity	- Economy: a breakdown by sub-agricultural sector could be useful, as "agriculture" is a very diverse sector. Some ag sectors perform better than others (e.g. grains vs. livestock)
	Sectoral wages	- also distribution of salary sector
	Market organisation	- Farmers bargaining power in supply chain
	Trade	- Trade volume in agriculture
	Energy access	- Also maybe Energy access can be divided in heating/electricity/fuel
	Other	- R&D spending per country on agriculture and nature innovation - Turnover per sector. - Price indices of agricultural production inputs - resilience of the economy to big disruptions affecting trade
Farm resilience	Farm income	
	Farm viability	- Could we consider farm digitalization instead of modernisation? It is more specific and more sustainable
	Farm structure	- Type of farming structures / Owners of the land : individual farm, cooperative forms, private company...
	Other	- for farm resilience: mental health and farm diversification - combination of plant and animal production on one farm - For Farm resilience also productivity per sector - not only employees but also family members which are working there
Social equity	Income distribution (sectoral, spatial)	
	Education	

Thematic area	Indicator Domain	Responses to “Which indicator domain do you miss in the thematic area ...”
	Gender equality	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - % of women-led agriculture and rural enterprises - Proportion of women managing farms in agriculture
	Other	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Access to basic services in rural areas - access to public infrastructures (transport...) - missing indicators on the living, economical and working condition of guest workers

7.2. Modelling Workshop (Hybrid, March 2024)

Following the first thematic seminar, the received comments and recommendations were used to refine the SJOS framework. Subsequently, a workshop with the modelling teams involved in the BrightSpace toolbox (Figure 13) was organized in March 2024. One objective was to identify indicators, that are already included, or planned to be included, in the reporting routines of the models, and that fit into the indicator domains of the proposed SJOS. The respective results from this workshop are listed in Table 15 and Table 16. It appeared that almost all of the indicator domains are covered by at least one model-based indicator. In the SOS (Table 15), all indicator domains are covered, at least in the sense that the models are set up to permit a scenario analysis with the respective indicator as exogeneous setting. As an example, a certain model may not allow an endogenous switch between conventional and organic farming, but it could be possible to run the model using several assumptions about the share of organic farming in the sector and compare the endogenous results like area allocation or crop production levels, provided that the model already features a representation of organic production technologies and management practices.

The two indicator domains of the JOS missing in the toolbox models are animal welfare and access to clean water. In the case of the former, it could be possible to derive an index of animal welfare based on model results in the same way as e.g. the CAPRI and FarmDyn models report on contributions to biodiversity (Biodiversity friendly practices indicator). An example would be to account for grazing days, number of animals per ha of grassland, number of lactation periods, share of grassland products in the animal ration, and other model variables to derive an “animal welfare friendly practices” index. This is a typical example for explorative model adjustments that will take place within BrightSpace. Should such indexes prove to be acceptable, valid, and reliable, they will be included in the SJOS. In the case of access to clean water, this involves waste water treatment, water purification, distribution infrastructure, which are beyond the scope of sector- and economy-wide models in the toolbox and the additional effort to include this indicator could easily outweigh the validity of the constructed indicator. As in the case of animal welfare, this is part of the anticipated research work in BrightSpace.

Figure 13 BrightSpace model toolbox

Table 15 SOS Indicator domains and potential model indicators

Thematic area	Indicator Domain	Example Indicator(s)	Models
Biodiversity	Genetic/Functional diversity (outcomes)	Biodiversity Intactness Index (BII)	IMAGE, GLOBIOM
		Terrestrial Mean Species Abundance (MSA)	IMAGE
		Farmland Birds Index (FBI)	CAPRI
		Fraction of remaining species (cSAR)	GLOBIOM
	Land management (drivers)	Biodiversity friendly practices Indicator (BFP) / Paracchini-Britz index	CAPRI, FARMDYN
		Agricultural area under organic farming	GLOBIOM (scen.), AGMEMOD (scen.), CAPRI (dev.), FARMDYN (scen.)
		Crop diversity index	GLOBIOM, AGMEMOD, CAPRI, FARMDYN
		Area in Agri-Environmental Measures (excl. organic farming)	GLOBIOM (partly), AGMEMOD, CAPRI, FARMDYN
Land use	Land cover	Agricultural land covered with landscape features	CAPRI, FARMDYN (partly)
		Agricultural area (UAA)	IMAGE, GLOBIOM, MAGNET, AGMEMOD, CAPRI, FARMDYN (scen.)
		Forest and other wooded land (FOWL)	IMAGE, GLOBIOM, AGMEMOD (scen.), CAPRI
			IMAGE, GLOBIOM, AGMEMOD (scen.), CAPRI

Thematic area	Indicator Domain	Example Indicator(s)	Models
		Land cover (all other land cover types, including built-up areas, recreational area, ...)	
	Soil health	Tillage practices humus balance (drivers) crop yields (productivity)	FARMDYN (scen.)
Water use	Water use	Water abstraction in agriculture	IMAGE, GLOBIOM, MAGNET
		Irrigated land	IMAGE, GLOBIOM
Nutrient flows	Nitrogen cycle	Inorganic fertilizer Use Nitrogen Organic fertilizer application Nitrogen Gross nitrogen balance	IMAGE, GLOBIOM, CAPRI, FARMDYN
	Phosphorus cycle	Inorganic fertilizer Use Phosphorus Organic fertilizer application Phosphorus Gross phosphorus balance	IMAGE, CAPRI, FARMDYN IMAGE, CAPRI, FARMDYN IMAGE, GLOBIOM, CAPRI, FARMDYN
Chemical pollution (novel entities)	Pesticide use	Use of chemical pesticides	MAGNET, CAPRI, FARMDYN
		Use of more hazardous pesticides	CAPRI
	Antimicrobials	Use of antimicrobials in food producing animal	CAPRI (dev.)
Aerosol loading	Air pollution (Particulates)	Ammonia emissions	IMAGE, CAPRI, FARMDYN
Climate	Genetic/Functional diversity (outcomes)	GHG emissions agriculture, (CO ₂ e) Agr. Emissions - CO ₂ - CH ₄ - N ₂ O	IMAGE, MAGNET, GLOBIOM, AGMEMOD (dev) CAPRI, FARMDYN IMAGE, MAGNET, GLOBIOM, AGMEMOD (dev.), CAPRI, FARMDYN

Acronyms: TBD: To be determined / Scen.: Scenario can be implemented, exogenous / Dev.: Under development

Table 16 JOS Indicator domains and potential model indicators

Thematic area	Indicator Domain	Potential indicators	Models
Nutrition security	Food availability	Average dietary energy supply	CAPRI, GLOBIOM, MAGNET, AGMEMOD
	... affordability	Percent of the population that cannot afford a healthy diet Food price index Agro-food commodity prices, per type per MS	Microsimulation CAPRI, GLOBIOM, MAGNET, AGMEMOD
	... stability	Import dependency ratio Self-sufficiency rates	CAPRI, GLOBIOM, MAGNET, AGMEMOD

Thematic area	Indicator Domain	Potential indicators	Models
	Food waste	Food waste from harvest losses, food processing, transport and food waste from commodities and food services consumption	MAGNET, GLOBIOM (scen.)
	Diet quality/food utilization	Share of calories from fruit and vegetables Share of plant-based protein consumer intake in total protein consumer diet Distance to national dietary guidelines	CAPRI, GLOBIOM, MAGNET AGMEMOD MAGNET
Health	Life expectancy	Diet related mortality	Food & Health model
	Obesity	Prevalence of overweight/obesity	MAGNET, Food & Health model
	Animal welfare	TBD	TBD
	Access to clean water	TBD	TBD
Economy	Sectoral Employment	Number of workers per sector	MAGNET
	Sectoral productivity	Value added per sector Total factor productivity by sector	MAGNET MAGNET
	Sectoral wages	Factor prices labour	MAGNET
	Market organisation	Share of agricultural VA in total VA Agro-food commodity market structure per type and MS Agro-food commodity production volumes per type and MS	MAGNET AGMEMOD AGMEMOD
	Trade	Sectoral trade Agro-food commodity trade	CAPRI, GLOBIOM, MAGNET AGMEMOD
	Energy access	Energy price index	MAGNET
Farm resilience	Farm income	Farm income distribution	FARMDYN, based on samples
	Farm viability	Farm size distribution	FARMDYN, in combination with farm exit model
	Farm structure	TBD	TBD
Social equity	Income distribution (sectoral, spatial)	Gini index/Palma ratio	Microsimulation, MAGNET (indirectly)
	Education	Education levels	MAGNET (TBD)
	Gender equality	Gender wage gap	MAGNET (TBD)

Acronyms: TBD: To be determined / Scen.: Scenario can be implemented, exogenous / Dev.: Under development

7.3. Thematic Seminar on Biodiversity Indicators (Online, 11.04.2024)

One of the major goals of BrightSpace is to identify indicators for the different thematic areas, which can be calculated based on the models in the toolbox and are at the same time valid for the system they are supposed to measure. This is particularly challenging in the case of biodiversity because of the large amount of alternative direct and indirect indicators. A variety of additional possible indicators for biodiversity was recommended by the participants of the 1st Thematic seminar (Table 13), for instance direct measures like the pollinator index, the grassland butterfly index, or

measurements of invasive species. Suggested indirect measures were for instance the existence of landscape features and land configuration. These suggestions were discussed during the modelling workshop. Table 15 gives an overview on the direct and indirect measures for biodiversity that are already included in the BrightSpace model toolbox. Available direct measures are the Farmland Bird Index (FBI), the Biodiversity Intactness Index (BII), and the Mean Species Abundance (MSA) index. Indicators for particular groups of animals like the butterfly index or for certain species that are closely linked to agricultural landscapes like the European hamster (*Cricetus cricetus*) are not readily available. With regard to indirect measures, certain types of landscape features or area under environmental programmes can be modelled or at least included as exogeneous drivers for the models. A crucial point was whether tolerable ranges for biodiversity in the SJOS can be defined based on these indicators. Because of these questions, a second Thematic Seminar was organized with a special topic on biodiversity (“Defining the Safe Operating Space(s) regarding Biodiversity”, 11 April 2024, online). In addition to the participants of the first Thematic Seminar, further experts in the field of biodiversity were directly invited.

Five indicators were selected as basis for the discussion: Three direct indicators, which are included in the toolbox models (Table 15):

- Farmland birds index (FBI) (also a PMEF/CMEF context indicator)
- Mean Species Abundance (MSA)
- Biodiversity Intactness Index (BII)

In addition, two indirect indicators from the Common Evaluation and Monitoring Framework (CMEF 2019, Context indicators) were selected because of the availability of historical data and experience among the modelling teams to include them in scenario analyses:

- C34 Natura 2000 areas
- C36 Conservation status of agricultural habitats (grassland)

Historical development of these indicator were shown and the participants were asked to indicate on a Mural dashboard which values they would consider as border between a certainly risky and a possibly safe status for the respective indicator for biodiversity (“pain point”).

Figure 14 Mural dashboard for the Farmland bird index

Note: Historical values from CMEF 2019

Dashboard from <https://www.mural.co/>

The placing of the ‘pain points’ was repeated for the remaining four indicators as well. A critical question was, if the valuation of the system status as “unsafe” refers to the biosphere itself or the ability of the biosphere to support vital ecosystem services for human survival. The indicators chosen in the PB and Doughnut frameworks (chapter 2.1) refer to rates of biodiversity loss, i.e. the focus is on biodiversity as a whole, and not only on biodiversity providing services to humans. A second important point addressed the comparative advantages of indicators like the BII, which combines a larger number of species, and those referring to particular species (e.g. birds or butterflies) . The FBI, for instance, is considered as a good indicator for the overall state of biodiversity because of the position of birds in the food chain, which requires the existence of an ecosystem that can support the bird population. A potential risk is that the choice of particular species as indicators may draw the attention to these species and away from the system as a whole. However, the Birds and Habitats directives establish reporting obligations for MS for a number of species in addition to birds, some of which are tightly linked to agricultural landscapes like the European hamster. Including a list of such farmland species as biodiversity indicators in the SJOS provides a link to existing EU legislation and of building on pre-existing reporting obligations of the MS, so that historical data is available, which could be used to identify correlations or functional relations with certain model variables. This is a topic that will be explored further.

Additionally, the question arose whether general pain points could be identified at all at such big spatial scales for the biodiversity indicators and for biodiversity in general. The main concern in this regard was that the pain point would heavily depend on the reference year or the reference ecosystem, e.g., whether pristine ecosystems or organic farming. In response to these questions an internal discussion within the Brightspace project on setting pain points for biodiversity will be organized.

Several questions could not be answered directly, but they will be addressed in the preparation of the planned 1st Stakeholder Retreat in June 2024. Because the use of the dashboard efficiently elicited the

opinions of a large number of experts and stimulate discussion, this technique will also be applied for the other indicators during the stakeholder retreat.

In a subsequent round, participants were asked to make an assessment how useful (measured on a 1 (lowest)-5 (highest) scale) the respective indicators are to assess the biodiversity status and at the same time for setting a “pain point”. Figure 15 shows the average score for the discussed indicators as well as the score that was selected by the largest number of participants (mode).

Figure 15 Score for biodiversity indicators by participants

Note: The Question asked was: “How useful is the for assessing biodiversity status AND for setting a 'pain point' (where Unsafe range begins)?”

Based on these scores, the preferred indicators were the direct indicators BII and the FBI, followed by the indirect indicator “Conservation status of agricultural habitats”. Comments in the Mural on these indicators reveal that the preference for BII, a measure of biodiversity intactness, originates from the perception of stakeholders that biodiversity should be as intact as possible. Therefore, stakeholders uniformly chose a relatively high BII level close to the intact state (1) (Figure 16)

Stakeholders noted that the downside of using BII as an indicator is that no condition of intactness can be reached in agricultural areas, meaning that biodiversity can never resemble the level of pristine ecosystems. This is an argument for using FBI, as it directly measures biodiversity in agricultural areas based on representative indicator farmland bird species. Interestingly, the stakeholders were much more uniform in indicating the pain point for biodiversity for BII than for FBI, indicating that BII is more uniformly interpreted or fits better within the SJOS framework. It is important to note that there is no consensus that one indicator is completely suitable for setting a pain point. The results of the workshop reveal the potential need to consider multiple biodiversity indicators and set pain points for each of them.

8. CONCLUSIONS AND OUTLOOK

This report summarizes the work in the BrightSpace project to develop a monitoring framework for EU agriculture in the context of a Safe and Just operating space, which takes environmental boundaries and socio-economic requirements into accounts. Based on a literature review, a set of dimensions frequently used to define Safe and Just operating spaces was identified and compared with stated objectives from EU policy frameworks, namely the CAP and the European Green Deal and its strategies relevant for the agricultural sector, in particular the Farm to Fork and Biodiversity strategies. This framework was further refined based on existing monitoring systems like the PMEF and expert consultations within and outside of the project consortium. The proposed SJOS for EU agriculture consists of 12 thematic areas, further split into 34 indicator domains. Specific indicators for each domain were reviewed and examples for potential indicators from the BrightSpace model toolbox were identified, but are at this stage not finally decided as usually multiple indicators that can be applied within the respective indicator domains. In addition, several model adjustments to permit the calculation of additional indicators will take place within the duration of the project.

The next step is to include the identified indicators in the standard reporting of the respective models and derive ways to permit their comparison across the different methodological backgrounds of the models, as is done within AgMIP. This allows identifying indicator trajectories along the common baseline of the models until 2050. The results of the SJOS baseline projections will be discussed with the BrightSpace stakeholders during a retreat planned for June 2024. This will be the starting point for the identification of Safe and Just ranges for the identified indicators.

9. ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

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